

THE ROLE OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION IN TOURISM INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article will mainly analyze the role of intercultural communication in tourism industry in the development of Uzbekistan. The country is consistently implementing comprehensive measures to develop tourism as one of the strategic sectors of the national economy, ensuring its diversification and accelerated development of regions, creating new jobs, increasing incomes and the quality of life of the population, as well as improving investment attractiveness.

It is known that intercultural communication essentially means communication across different cultural boundaries. When two or more people with different cultural backgrounds interact and communicate with each other or one another, we can say that intercultural communication is taking place. Intercultural communication takes place when interacting participants represent a different communication system. Differences may occur in verbal and nonverbal communication, for instance, eye contact, gestures, touch, pauses, turn-taking or use of time. They are potential sources of clashes or conflicts in intercultural communication. In a case of an intercultural communication clash, there may occur feelings of confusion, tension, embarrassment and frustration. So intercultural communication can be defined as the sharing of information on

different levels of awareness between people with different cultural backgrounds, or put simply: individuals influenced by different cultural groups negotiate shared meaning in interactions. In Uzbekistan, also, intercultural communication plays a major role in the development of tourism industry as it improves not only country's economic situation, but also creates a great number of jobs for the population. In fact, currently, tourism is one of the leading sectors of the global economy. Therefore, Uzbekistan places particular emphasis on the modernization of the tourism industry, the development and improvement of the regulatory framework for the sustainable development of the industry, and the organization of tourist services in accordance with international standards. During the years of independence, significant actions were implemented in Uzbekistan in terms of the development of

this sphere with the preservation and enhancement of the historical and cultural heritage of the people, the revival of national traditions and customs, restoration and arrangement of the country's attractions. From the first years of independence, Uzbekistan has been actively increasing cooperation with international organizations, and regularly comes up with initiatives to deepen cooperation in the field of tourism. The current trend of the tourism industry confirms the need to study the prerequisites, system analysis of the dynamics of tourism development, identifying preferences and expectations of tourists, timely correction and modernization of the system of measures, taking into account the existing realities and prospects, which served as the basis for this study. In order to create a bond between different cultures around the world, not only language can serve as a helpful way here, but also intercultural communication with tourist destinations can help to create the atmosphere of camaraderie between countries. In order to improve the intercultural communication, the system of preparing good personnel in tourism is a vital priority in Uzbekistan nowadays. In fact, preparing experienced and multi lingual guides and translators is becoming more and more important in order to attract and make tourists interested in our culture and mentality. Thus, this will help to boost the economic situation of the country. Today it is the largest forum in Central Asia where industry professionals meet, negotiate in various formats, including business-to-business, the Hosted Buyers program is being implemented for buyers of the national tourist product, and conferences

are being held on topical issues of the development of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan and the world generally. Representatives of our country also regularly participate in international fairs and exhibitions held abroad in order to present the tourist potential of the republic. Participation in them allows you to stay abreast of the latest trends in the global tourism market, enter into business contracts, and develop cooperation with foreign partners.

After looking at some special side intercultural communication in tourism, the following conclusions can be drawn. First of all, it is dynamic to pay special attention to the developing intercultural communication in tourism industry and to create a wide range of opportunities. The next ten out of every four new jobs per year is employed by the tourism sector across the country. Then, it also contributes significantly to the reduction of unemployment rate. This, in turn, can lead to get a high income for the population and it is also considered as the source of income. Especially short trips, urban tourism, gastronomic tourism and pilgrimage tourism development, urban infrastructure development, variety construction of hotels, and restaurants improve services, for tourist shopping production of assortment of demanding products. These are just some of the goal setting that we can use including tourism and transport infrastructure, as well as the world – famous hotel business providing benefits, including chains attracting foreign direct investment. Secondly, like modern and branded hotels, hostels, family hotels, budget accommodations, as well as from the Airbnb system (renting apartments,

using the introduction of this system) should be accelerated.

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